

MAELSTROM

Smart technology for MARine Litter SusTainable
RemOval and Management

D9.3

First Interim communication and dissemination report

11/07/2022

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1 Executive Summary

The present document refers to the First Interim Communication and Dissemination Report of the EU-funded project MAELSTROM – Smart technology for MArinE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management.

The document is deliverable 9.3 of Work Package 9 and intends to inform the European Commission and the MAELSTROM consortium of the communication and dissemination activities implemented during the first 18 months. Although communication and dissemination activities are complementary, we have preferred to treat them as two separate chapters for the purpose of reporting. In this regard, we will be referring to communication as past and ongoing efforts to create strategic opportunities for promoting the project, its relevance, and its milestones to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, engaging in a two-way exchange; we will be referring to dissemination as the past and ongoing efforts to promote and facilitate the use of MAELSTROM's research and technological results among potential users and peers within the research, industry, commercial and policy-making fields.

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2 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM - *Smart technology for MARine Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management* is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex question of the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy. MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with fully-fledged circular economy and society-oriented solutions. In particular, the project

- (i) sets out a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas.
- (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable, and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second-generation fuel, to identify, remove, and sort marine litter.
- (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems.
- (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation.
- (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of MAELSTROM solutions, also providing a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products.
- (vi) enhances social awareness on the issue of marine litter and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities.
- (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

3 MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of the following partners

Table 1 - MAELSTROM partners

	National Research Council	CNR	Project Coordinator Fantina MADRICARDO fantina.madricardo@ismar.cnr.it
	Deltares	Deltares	Frans BUSCHMAN Frans.Buschman@deltares.nl
	University of Malta	UOM	Luciano MULE' STAGNO luciano.mule-stagno@um.edu.mt
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	Gees Recycling Srl	GEES	Giorgio BETTETO geesretracking@gmail.com
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	CIMA Research Foundation	CIMA	Isabel GOMES isabel.gomes@cimafoundation.org
	TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION	TECNALIA	Damien SALLÉ damien.salle@tecnalia.com
	ALPHA Consult	ALPHA UK	Emiliano SPALTRO es@alphacons.eu
	Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research	CIIMAR	Isabel SOUSA-PINTO ispinto@ciimar.up.pt
	Servizi Tecnici	ST	Nicola FERRARI n.ferrari@stvenezia.com
	The Great Bubble Barrier	TGBB	Philip EHRHORN philip@thegreatbubblebarrier.com
	MAKEEN	MAKEEN	Anders BJORN ABJ@makeenenergy.com
	National Center for Scientific Research	CNRS	Marc GOUTTEFARDE marc.gouttefarde@lirmm.fr

4 Aim of the Deliverable

The present document refers to the First Interim Communication and Dissemination Report of the EU-funded project MAELSTROM. The document is Deliverable 9.3 of Work Package 9 and provides an overview of the main activities and actions related to communication and dissemination efforts put in place during the first 18 months of the project.

The basis of this document is D.91. **“Plan of Dissemination and Communication”** delivered in June 2021, which sets a preliminary strategy and work plan for the communication and dissemination activities foreseen within the MAELSTROM project. Besides providing an overview of the participation and representation of MAELSTROM at physical and online events, relevant publications, networking and social media performance, the present document also describes the adaptation measures which were put in place to address the communication and dissemination needs of MAELSTROM's consortium during this period.

Work Package 9 – Communication and Dissemination includes five tasks as illustrated in Figure 1:

Task 9.1. - Communication and Dissemination Plans

Task 9.2. - Project Branding & Media

Task 9.3. - Support Capacity Building Actions

Task 9.4. – Support Stakeholder Engagement Processes

Task 9.5. – Support Project's events

Figure 1- Communication and Dissemination Tasks

5 Communication and Dissemination Plan: general update

During the first 18 months, a significant effort was devoted to communicating and disseminating project activities, findings, and outcomes to the wider community. From public events to scientific conferences, press articles and networking actions, both planned activities and new opportunities were fully taken by the MAELSTROM consortium. Activities have followed the guidelines presented within the Plan for Communication and Dissemination delivered on date 06/2021.

Although MAELSTROM technologies are still being developed and the main achievements and results are expected to happen by the end of 2022 and during 2023, the project's visibility has so far followed a positive trend, with a growing number of invitations to participate at public and technical events and requests for information/collaboration and networking. The consortium has also reached out to other projects and initiatives in the field, in order to promote an open collaboration and a synergic flow among EU-funded projects. MAELSTROM's webinars played a key role in establishing fruitful connections among the international community working in marine litter-related fields and across relevant stakeholders. While we wait for dissemination activities to expand in the following months, in this first year and a half emphasis was given to the project's branding and to the identification of key communication stakeholders. Together with partner CIIMAR, at the end of 2021 and within Work Package 7, the communication team has developed a *Joint Strategy for Dissemination and Networking Activities on Marine Litter*. This was an occasion to map relevant stakeholders which will be gradually engaged by CIIMAR as part of the stakeholder engagement activities foreseen in WP7.

At the end of 2021, due to a partnership established between one of our partners - The Great Bubble Barrier and the Engie Foundation, in which the Engie Foundation is expected to sponsor part of the implementation of the Bubble Barrier in the Ave River in Portugal - the consortium has expressed the need to establish communication and dissemination procedures regarding third-party involvement. After a dedicated meeting between the Project Manager (CNR-ISMAR) and the Project Officer, the WP9 Leader/Communication Manager proposed a set of guidelines which were shared with the consortium's communication focal points in a dedicated meeting on 21/01/2022. After collecting and integrating feedback received from partners, the procedures were approved in unanimity. A detailed explanation of these procedures is reported in **ANNEX 1**.

6 Communication strategy: update for M18

During the first eighteen months, MAELSTROM's communication actions aimed to promote the project's objectives and activities in a clear and intelligible way to multiple stakeholders, including civil society at large. In alignment with the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, the 2030 Agenda and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSDF), MAELSTROM's communication efforts focus on raising awareness within civil society regarding the impact of marine litter and plastic pollution, responsible behaviours, and removal solutions.

Although the communication coordinator - CIMA Research Foundation - bears leadership of communication activities, all partners support and pro-actively engage in these efforts. Strong linkages with partner Venice Lagoon Plastic Free, leading the In-No-Plastic project communication activities and with vast experience on public awareness events, are already in place and expected to continue throughout the project duration. Linkages with CNR-ISMAR's past and present activities in the plastics field, alongside initiatives with artists and schools from Venice, are strongly supported by CIMA's Communication Department.

Citizens, Young Generations and Local Administrations are targeted as key players, towards which we aim to fostering a reflection on the implications of plastic production and plastic consumerism, citizen responsibility and circular economy. This is achieved mainly during public events/info days, and through the publication of our **MAELDROPS**: pills of information regarding the impact of marine litter and plastic pollution, graphically illustrated and published on social media every 1.5/2 months. Requests from local and international journalists (e. g. *The Guardian*) and from the *Horizon EU Magazine* have resulted in three international articles; as soon as the MAELSTROM technologies are developed and in place, similar requests are expected to also increase. TV channels such as *Euro News* have already expressed their interest in following the project outcomes in Venice. This will certainly contribute to the overall visibility of the project and will further support awareness on the way audiences perceive marine litter, and how they can become part of the global efforts towards sustainable oceans and societies. Finally, the MAELSTROM project will directly and actively contribute to the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030" which aims, in the next decade, to restore ecosystems and biodiversity, eliminating pollution, and making the blue economy carbon-neutral and circular .

6.1 Media & Branding | Task 9.2

Due to the highly communicative potential of the MAELSTROM project, initial efforts have focused on creating a strong and attractive project brand. MAELSTROM's logo represents, through its lines, shapes, and colours, some of the natural elements and settings related to the project's implementation and activities. The logo was studied to perform well in multiple formats, from traditional paper printing to T-shirts, web usage, apps, and a stamp for eventual gadgets.

Figure 2 - MAELSTROM Logo visual elements

Considering the amount of foreseen project events and the multiple invitations received by the consortium to participate at external initiatives, a multimedia package was designed and shared with partners in the early months of 2021 and is constantly updated based on partners' needs. During 2022, a trilingual brochure was also produced with more in-depth details regarding the project's aims, technologies, and public events (clean-ups). English, Italian, and Portuguese were the languages chosen, as they represent the consortium's language, English, and the languages of the two pilot areas, Italy and Portugal, where the MAELSTROM's technologies are expected to be implemented and where local stakeholder involvement is of utmost importance.

Table 2 - Branding Materials list

Event's kit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logo • Leaflet and Brochure • PPT, Word and Poster templates • Roll-ups and flags • T-shirt and Bags
Videos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to the project - 2021 • MAELSTROM App - July 2022 • Bubble Barrier @Portugal (short) - July 2022 • Bubble Barrier @Portugal (long) - 2022/TBC • The Underwater Robot @Venice (short) - September 2022 • The Underwater Robot @Venice (long) - September 2022 • Final Conference video 2023/24
Newsletters (see ANNEX 3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter 1 - 06/2021 • Newsletter 2 - 12/2021 • Newsletter 3 - 06/2022 • Newsletter 4 - 12/2022 • Newsletter 5 - 06/2023 • Newsletter 6 - 12/2023 • Newsletter 7 - 06/2024 • Newsletter 8 - 12/2024
Website	http://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu
Social Media	Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter and Instagram
MAELDrops	Nine pills of information on key topics relating to marine litter, plastic pollution, circular economy and recycling innovations have been designed and published on both the MAELSTROM website and on social media channels.
Whale sculptures	Three models built and delivered, one in Portugal and two in Italy

Press outreach	https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-press-review/
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Events Kit

MAELSTROM's events kit was designed to adapt to formal (e.g. conferences) and informal events (such as clean-ups). It includes internal and external roll-ups, brochures, flags, T-shirts, bags and document templates which are openly available to the consortium's partners through the dedicated MS Teams channel, the SeedsDMS repository and on the MAELSTROM website, under the media kit section (<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstorm-media-kit/>).

Printing of materials is reduced to the necessary minimum quantities due to its environmental impact and is done when no other (digital) alternatives are possible; eco-printing is strongly encouraged. Other gadgets have so far not been considered necessary or useful.

Videos

Six to seven videos illustrating the different steps of the project are foreseen as part of MAELSTROM's multimedia package. A first video to present the project was made in 2021 and projected during *the 1st International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy*, held in Venice during the International Boat Show. The video used an infographic approach as no "real" footage could yet be taken. As we write, two short videos with real images from the project are being edited: the first regards the MAELSTROM app and the second regards the implementation of the Bubble Barrier in the Ave River which was partially projected during the UN Ocean Conference held in June, in Lisbon. The aim is to use these short videos on social media and at relevant events.

Two more comprehensive videos illustrating the two MAELSTROM technologies are expected to be concluded by the end of the year once the implementation period is also concluded. Finally, a conclusive video of the project's highlights is expected to be produced and shown during the final conference, which will take place in Portugal in 2024. Local video companies, both in Italy and in Portugal, have been contracted to produce the videos with the guidance of CIMA Research Foundation and the

logistical support of the partners responsible for the technologies' development and implementation.

Newsletters

Biannual newsletters are delivered every six months to the MAELSTROM Consortium and to interested subscribers. Newsletters consist of a summary of concluded project activities or milestones and announcements of future events. During 2021, two newsletters were produced and sent in June and December. A third newsletter is expected to be sent by July 2022 and a fourth by the end of December 2022. It is possible to subscribe to MAELSTROM's newsletter by filling in the dedicated form on the project website (homepage). Data protection on subscription is guaranteed in accordance with GDPR from 2018.

Newsletters archive: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-newsletters/>

Website

Alongside social media accounts, MAELSTROM's website is the main source of information regarding project activities, events, and milestones. With an average of 910 new users during a 90-day period, it has achieved a positive outreach. Most new users during the month of June 2022 were from Italy (111), Portugal (61), United States (33) and The Netherlands (26). The pages which are mostly visited are the homepage, followed by the page "What does MAELSTROM do?", and the page dedicated to the explanation of removal technologies. Peaks on site visits happen when sharing an article on social media or near the date of an event. For this reason, we have decided to increment our social media presence so as to maintain and increase our online community. In this regard, partners have been asked to share their activities more often with the communication team, which will follow up with developing dedicated interviews, posts, and/or news articles.

Website: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/>

Figure 3 - MAELSTROM's website views and users during the month of June 2022

Social media

Social network accounts on LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter and Instagram were created for the MAELSTROM project as they offer good opportunities of reaching multiple audiences and engaging them with the project's dissemination and awareness goals. MAELSTROM's social media profiles have two main goals:

- To disseminate MAELSTROM's scientific and technological outcomes.
- To foster citizen awareness on marine litter, single-use plastics and circular economy possibilities.

Similar to MAELSTROM's website, the social media profiles present a positive trend, even though the digital community is still small (average 130/140 followers per social media profile) in the last 90-day period, post coverage has reached an average of 904 people on Instagram and 4053 on Facebook, resulting in 635 new visits to our accounts. Similarly, Twitter and LinkedIn present positive trends, with 3598 impressions and 24 new followers in a 28-day period analysis.

Efforts will be made to increase the number of social media followers, and their engagement and interaction with the project's activities.

Facebook and Instagram

Reach

Facebook Page reach ⓘ

4,053 ↑ 499.6%

Instagram reach ⓘ

904 ↑ 347.5%

New likes and follows

Facebook Page new likes ⓘ

8 ↑ 33.3%

Instagram new followers ⓘ

34 ↑ 79.9%

Page and profile visits

Facebook Page visits ⓘ

264 ↑ 380%

Instagram profile visits ⓘ

371 ↑ 657.1%

Figure 4 - MAELSTROM's Facebook and Instagram visits (above) and coverage (below) in a 90-day period April 2021 to July 2022

Twitter

Figure 5 - MAELSTROM's Twitter impressions and visits, 28-day summary (by 06/07/2022)

LinkedIn

Figure 6 - MAELSTROM's LinkedIn post new followers in the last during the 30-day period between June 2022 to July 2022

MAELDrops

Aiming at making topics on marine litter, plastic pollution, circular economy, and recycling innovations accessible to as many people as possible, CIMA's communication team has created an editorial project called MAELDrops, short "pills" of information accompanied by graphic illustrations, which are posted every 1.5/2 months. Sources of information to feed the MAELDrops come from scientific papers, reports by the EU, UN and accredited websites. MAELDrops' aim is to translate technical information into accessible communication materials which are useful to

our audiences, while creating awareness and encouraging citizen engagement. Since the beginning of the project, nine MAELDrops have been designed and published both on the MAELSTROM website and on its social media channels. Annex 2 contains all published MAELDrops content and visuals for consultation.

Figure 7 - MAELDROP n. 9 - Nexus among COVID-19 and plastic production

Recycled Whale Statues

Three real-sized plastic sperm whale installations were created with recycled plastic provided by the Ecopolietilene consortium with whom the project has established an MoU.

The reason for choosing a sperm whales (*Physeter macrocephalus*) made of polyethylene as mascots for our project is because sperm whales, like other marine mammals, are endangered and particularly threatened by plastic marine litter.

Dozens of these whales die every year due to inflammation caused by the presence of indigestible plastic in their stomach or due to entanglement in ghost (plastic-made) nets. More than 640,000 tonnes of nets, lines, pots, and traps used in commercial fishing are dumped and discarded in the sea every year; most of this material is made of polyethylene. Like other types of plastic, polyethylene is a non-biodegradable material, which uses considerable amounts of fossil fuels to be produced and takes centuries to decompose. It is therefore imperative to reduce its use and to recycle it as much as possible.

As part of MAELSTROM's communication activities, three life-size whales were delivered to Portugal (1) and Italy (2) and showcased during the 2021 clean-up event in Porto and during MAELSTROM's *Second International Workshop on the Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy*, held in Venice during the International Boat Show at the beginning of June 2022. The team is now looking for a suitable long-term location for the third whale, ensuring that it will be used as an educational tool to raise awareness on the impacts of marine litter in ecosystems and the advantages of a circular economy paradigm.

Figure 8 - MAELSTROM's recycled plastic sperm whale in Porto, during World Clean Up Day, 17/09/2021

Figure 9 - MAELSTROM's recycled plastic sperm whale in Venice at CNR-ISMAR headquarters, Italy.

Press and online articles

Several articles regarding MAELSTROM's events have been published by local newspapers in Italy and in Portugal and can be consulted on the project website under the section Media – Press Review:

(<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-press-review/>).

The project was also featured in three international publications, with two dedicated articles in EU *Horizon Magazine* and one in *The Guardian*. Moreover, MAELSTROM was also featured on the CORDIS Synergy Info Pack.

- CORDIS Synergy Info Pack: Restore our oceans and water
https://ec.europa.eu/info/news/out-now-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-synergyinfo-pack-cordis-2022-feb-16_en
- 11/01/2022 - Meet Mr. Trash Wheel – and the other new devices that eat river plastic
<https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2022/jan/11/meet-mr-trash-wheel-and-the-other-ingenious-tools-that-eat-river-plastic>
- 12/02/2022 - How robots and bubbles could soon help clean up underwater litter:
<https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/horizon-magazine/how-robots-and-bubbles-could-soon-help-clean-underwater-litter>

- 09/02/2022 - Beach bots, sea 'raptors' and marine toolsets mobilised to get rid of marine litter: <https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/horizon-magazine/beach-bots-sea-raptors-and-marine-toolsets-mobilised-get-rid-marine-litter>

7 Dissemination strategy: an update for M18

As already mentioned, MAELSTROM technologies are still being developed and main dissemination efforts are expected to happen towards the end of 2022 and during 2023 and 2024. However, in the first 18 months of the project, the MAELSTROM team has engaged in several technical events, capacity-building actions, and scientific communications. The communication team works alongside the consortium in these occasions, as they represent important opportunities to share project goals and preliminary results, which reinforce networking and synergy among peers and other multi-level stakeholders. Thus, although not directly responsible for the following tasks, CIMA's team has provided its technical support.

7.1 Support Capacity building actions | Task 9.3

MAELSTROM's capacity-building actions focus on three groups:

1. **Project partners:** a capacity building workshop for MAELSTROM's communication focal points was foreseen during the project's kick-off meeting.
2. **MAELSTROM app's interested users:** during project clean-ups and info days, MAELSTROM partners showcase features and functionalities of the MAELSTROM app to environmental associations, volunteers, and marine litter practitioners. The app is not designed for the general public, as it requires some knowledge regarding the different types of plastics.
3. **Operators and beneficiaries of MAELSTROM technologies:** such as waste management companies and municipalities in the pilot locations.

Foreseen capacity-building actions towards MAELSTROM's communication focal points were substituted by a monthly communication meeting, due to existing COVID-19 constraints at the date of the kick-off meeting. During these monthly communication meetings, partners have the chance to align on main milestones, events, and future actions, as well as make requests and or/discuss ideas relevant to project communication and dissemination activities. It was during one of these communication meetings that the communication team suggested the creation of two scale models illustrating the MAELSTROM technologies, which could be easily transported and showcased during conferences and public events. Partners Tecnalía and The Great Bubble Barrier both agreed to produce these models using their own

resources. Tecnalía used a 3D printer to assemble a mini seabed cleaning platform which was exhibited during MAELSTROM's *Second International Workshop on Marine Litter Removal and Circular Economy* held in June 2022 during Venice's International Boat Show.

Figure 10 - Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform presented by Damien Sallè from Tecnalía at the 2nd International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy, Venice, 1st June 2022

Similarly, the Bubble Barrier scale model was widely showcased during the recent United Nations Ocean Conference, held in Lisbon from the 27th June to the 1st July.

Figure 11 - Anne Marieke Eveleens from The Great Bubble Barrier demonstrates the Bubble Barrier system using a small-scale model at the United Nations Ocean Conference, Lisbon 28th June 2022

Regarding the capacity building actions foreseen for interested app users, MAELSTROM partner Venice Lagoon Plastic Free has conducted several clean-up activities in Venice where it has shared the features and functionalities of the MAELSTROM app to a wide range of local associations and volunteers willing to contribute to a marine litter open database, compliant with international standards. At the same time, MAELSTROM partners engaged in marine litter collection for research purposes in Portugal, Spain, and the Netherlands are using the MAELSTROM app on a continuous basis. On this regard, the MAELSTROM team in Portugal as partnered with Trash Traveler Initiative (<https://theplastichike.org/the-trash-cycle/>) and organized a joint clean up activity in Vila do Conde, in the northern region of Portugal, where the MAELSTROM app was presented and broadly used by local environmental associations.

To support the dissemination efforts, the communication team is producing a presentation video to publicize and disseminate the app during events to other possible interested users.

o **The Trash Traveller** percorre 2000km por Portugal numa bicicleta restaurada recolhendo lixo e garrafas de plástico, sem usar plástico descartável

The Trash CYCLE & MAELSTROM

A Tour to raise awareness to take care of the planet!

3 JUNHO VILA DO CONDE

Com:

- ICBAS
- CIIMAR - UP
- Mar de Experiências
- Dharma Yoga
- SUP Ramos
- Clube Fluvial Vilacondense
- Porto Surf School
- Surf In
- Escola de Música da Vila

18h - Encontro junto à Nau Quinhentista
 . Mostra de arte com lixo marinho - "Mar de Experiências"
 . Ensaio de guitarra e ukulele sobre o ambiente

Apresentação do MAELSTROM - projeto europeu pioneiro com nova tecnologia de limpeza de lixo marinho por investigadores do CIIMAR

18h30 - Limpeza e recolha de lixo
 Percurso pela zona ribeirinha até à praia N. Sra. da Guia

19h15 Demonstração de App para monitorizar lixo
 Sessão de Yoga - em frente ao CMIA

Junta-te a nós!
 e traz algo reutilizável!

Contacto em Vila do Conde
 Mariana Mota | Dlatz Ortega
 962 387 492 | ladoverdodavida.com@gmail.com

* info: theplastichike.org/the-trash-cycle | www.maelstrom-h2020.eu

Co-funded by the European Union

Figure 12 - The Trash Cycle and MAESLTROM joint clean up poster

Figure 13 - MAELSTROM's capacity-building activities for use of the MAELSTROM App with environmental associations in Venice

Finally, capacity-building actions targeting operators and beneficiaries of the MAELSTROM technologies will be implemented after deployment of the technologies in the pilot locations in Italy and in Portugal. Upon deployment, the communication team will provide support through the creation of dedicated material and presentations.

7.2 Support Stakeholder Engagement Processes | Task 9.4

MAELSTROM actively looks for the creation of synergy among multi-level actors relating to the marine litter cycle field. Those include similar and complementary EU and national projects, partnerships with relevant public or private actors - such as municipalities and waste management and recycling companies - academics, NGOs, artists, and local associations that might be interested in connecting with and supporting the project.

Stakeholder engagement and networking activities are led by Portuguese partner CIIMAR for activities in Portugal and by partners Venice Lagoon Plastic Free (VLPF) and CNR for activities in Italy. However, stakeholder engagement activities often meet with communication and dissemination efforts and thus CIIMAR, VLPF, CNR and CIMA work in close synergy. Below are some major networking achievements, which will be further detailed in CIIMAR's and CNR's reporting.

- Two stakeholder engagement webinars were organized by the MAELSTROM partners CIIMAR, CNR, VLPF and CIMA with the support and participation of other partners. The first webinar was held in November 2021 and focused on the theme: “*Science and society: working together to address the marine litter challenge*”. It served as a basic analysis of the Joint Strategy for Dissemination and Networking Activities on Marine Litter delivered by CIMA in December 2021 under Work Package 7 (lead by CIIMAR). The second webinar focused on “*Building Capacity in Detecting, Tracking and Modelling Marine Litter through European Open Science Cloud (#EOSC) Digital Services*”. Both counted with the participation of several international stakeholders to whom the consortium has established an open dialogue for future collaborations.

- A stakeholder meeting was organized in Venice with local stakeholders to highlight the current marine litter management system in Venice, considering the recent approval of the Italian ‘Salvamare’ regulation, which marks a turning point for the circular economy of marine litter in Italy. Activities and efforts of various European projects were presented, each supporting the technological and cultural step needed towards sustainable marine litter management in Italy and across Europe.

Figure 14 – Local Stakeholder Engagement Event, Venice, 31st May 2022

- A demonstrative session on the marGnet and MAELSTROM projects was organized by CNR to highlight the potential use of collected marine litter and the pyrolysis processes able to convert it into second-generation fuels to be used, for example, by local fisherman.
- The document “*Joint Strategy for Dissemination and Networking Activities on Marine Litter*” was produced and delivered by 12/2021 by CIMA's team with guidance from CIIMAR under Work Package 7. The document received inputs from November's webinar discussions and presented recommendations for capitalizing efforts regarding marine litter dissemination and networking across multiple actors.
- A Memorandum of Understanding was established with the Ecopolietilene Consortium (<https://ecopolietilene.it/>): an Italian group composed of manufacturers, distributors, and recyclers of polyethylene goods. The Ecopolietilene Consortium is an autonomous non-profit system recognized by the Italian Ministry of the Environment, Land and Sea Protection. The consortium has provided the recycled plastic material from which our life-size whale models were built.

- A Memorandum of Understanding was established between the University of Bologna and Tecnalìa for the mentorship of a PhD student at Tecnalìa's headquarters.
- The collaboration with our sister project In-No-Plastic translated into several synergies regarding communication activities, such as shared social media posts, shared press releases, and shared events.
- Other EU-funded projects and groups working in the marine litter field were contacted by the consortium and participated at MAELSTROM's workshops and events. Below is a list of engaged projects and institutions with which we have established an open dialogue regarding marine litter and plastic pollution:

Table 3 - EU funded projects engaged in MAELSTROM's events

Projects	
EU H2020 Claim	https://www.claim-h2020project.eu/
EU H2020 GoJelly	https://gojelly.eu/
EU H2020 SeaClear	https://seaclear-project.eu/
ITA-HR INTERREG MARLESS	https://www.italy-croatia.eu/web/marless
marGnet Consortium	https://www.margnet.eu/it/home/
BluMed Initiative	http://www.blumed-initiative.eu/
H2020 Reliance	https://www.reliance-project.eu/

Table 4 - Institutional actors engaged in MAELSTROM events

Institutional Actors	
Porto Municipality	https://www.cm-porto.pt/
Venice Municipality	https://www.comune.venezia.it/
Lipor – waste management body in Northern Portugal	https://www.lipor.pt/pt/
Gruppo Veritas - waste management body in Venice	https://www.gruppovertas.it/
Aguas do Norte – water management body in Northern Portugal	https://www.adnorte.pt/
Venice Coast Guard	https://www.guardiacostiera.gov.it/organizzazione/direzione-marittima-di-venezias
Veneto Region	https://www.regione.veneto.it/

ARPA Veneto (Veneto Environmental Agency)	https://www.arpa.veneto.it/
Provveditorato Interregionale per le Opere Pubbliche per il Veneto, Trentino-Alto Adige e Friuli-Venezia Giulia	http://provveditoratovenezia.mit.gov.it/
Senator Andrea Ferrazzi, member of the Italian Parliament	https://www.senato.it/leg/18/BGT/Schede/Attsen/00032632.htm
WWF Italy	https://www.wwf.it/

Table 5 - Private companies engaged in MAELSTROM Events

Companies	
Ecopolietilene Consortium (Italy)	https://ecopolietilene.it/
River Cleaning (Italy)	https://rivercleaning.com/it/
Clera.One (Slovenia)	https://www.clera.one/
WasteShark (The Netherlands)	https://www.wevolver.com/specs/wasteshark
Sintol Srl (Italy)	https://sintol.it/
Everwave (Germany)	https://everwave.de/en/
Caracol & NextChem (Italy)	https://nextchem.it
IRIS (Italy)	https://www.irissrl.eu
Fish Flow (The Netherlands)	https://fishflowinnovations.nl/en/
Nanobay (Germany)	https://www.nanobay.com/
Probotica (Croatia)	https://www.probotica.hr/
NNL (Greece)	https://www.oilspillresponse.gr/
Ponikve (Croatia)	http://www.ekootokkrk.hr/en
Empower (Norway)	https://www.empower.eco/
EMI (Italy)	https://emiforpets.it

MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic collaboration

MAELSTROM is meant to closely cooperate with its sister project In-No-Plastic, under the same call (ID: H2020-FNR-2020 - Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter). Both projects will contribute to the goal of the UN Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development aiming at “*a clean ocean where sources of pollution are identified and removed*”.

In this light, maximum cooperation between In-No-Plastic and MAELSTROM consortiums is and will continue to be pursued. This will be particularly relevant for stakeholder engagement, communication, and dissemination efforts. The benefits of having a common task force among the two teams are multiple:

- to create synergy between both projects towards disseminating a culture of awareness regarding the impact of marine litter on coastal ecosystems, within both projects’ pilot geographical areas and beyond.
- to promote and give visibility to the experimentation of different innovative technological solutions for the removal and recycling of marine litter, within a sustainable circular economy approach.
- to promote the transfer and adoption of In-No-Plastic and MAELSTROM technologies by local administrators, showing their environmental and social benefits.
- to optimize resources, ideas, creativity, and efforts between both projects’ communications teams.
- to widely highlight the multiple efforts being made towards a common goal - *to tackle marine litter* - with the full support of the European Union.

7.3 Support public and scientific events | Task 9.5

MAELSTROM's public events take place mainly in Italy and Portugal, and are managed by local partners CIIMAR, CNR-ISMAR, VLPF, and ISDN with the technical and communicative support of CIMA. Highlighting this is MAELSTROM's recent participation at the United Nations Ocean Conference held in Lisbon from 27th June to 1st July 2022, where the consortium had the exceptional opportunity to network and to present the project and its technologies. Considering the event was held in Portugal, a pilot country for the MAELSTROM project, emphasis was given to the Bubble Barrier system, soon to be installed in the Northern region of Portugal, and to the MAELSTROM app, a universal tool to monitor the full marine litter collection-recycling process.

The project was represented physically by partners from CIIMAR, Venice Lagoon Plastic Free, and The Great Bubble Barrier, while CNR and CIIMAR partners joined the online High-Level Conference "*Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030*". Moreover, MAELSTROM had dedicated slots at two UN side events and a dedicated slot on CIIMAR's stand as follows:

June 25th "Localizing Action for the Ocean: Local and Regional Governments Special Event-2022 United Nations Ocean Conference"

<https://sdgs.un.org/events/LRGspecialevent-2022UNOC>

- Portugal Implementing an Innovative Technology to Tackle Plastic Pollution with a Bubble Barrier.

June 27th "Official Session Addressing Marine Pollution"

<https://sdgs.un.org/events/addressing-marine-pollution-45736>

- Statement made by The Great Bubble Barrier on behalf of projects MAELSTROM and InNoPlastic. One of 5 stakeholders selected to speak, from 250 applicants.
- Written statement submitted by MAELSTROM and InNoPlastic to support the global discussions on marine litter: [Stakeholder Eng Prep Con | UN Ocean Conference | United Nations](#)

June 28th "One Sustainable Ocean-Ocean Science & Business2Sea Side Event" |

<https://onesustainableocean.forumoceano.pt/>

- Portugal Implementing an Innovative Technology to Tackle Plastic Pollution with a Bubble Barrier.
- Tackling the Marine Litter Management Cycle with the MAELSTROM app.

June 29th “Integrating Marine Litter Monitoring to Inform Action Side Event” | <https://www.eu4oceanobs.eu/marine-litter-monitoring-to-inform-action/>

- Live Demo Tackling the Marine Litter with the MAELSTROM App
- Live Demo Bubble Barrier Local Solutions for Marine Litter removal - Bubble Barrier

June 30th MAELSTROM Live Demos at CIIMAR’s stand and participation at the High-Level Conference: The Charter for the Mission “Restores our Ocean and Waters by 2030”

Figure 15 - MAELSTROM partners at the UN Ocean Conference Side Event, Matosinhos, June 25th, 2022

Other relevant events took place during the first eighteen months of the project and a significant effort was made to be able to represent MAELSTROM in all of them, using each occasion to network and engage audiences with our project goals. The tables

below summarize main events related to MAELSTROM activities: i) table 1 refers to official MAELSTROM events, organized by the consortium; ii) table 2 refers to external events where MAELSTROM was invited and represented by its partners.

Table 6 - MAELSTROM Events (Task 9.5)

	Title	Status	N. participants
Kick-off meeting	MAELSTROM Kick Off Meeting (online)	03-04-05/02/2021	All consortium members, an average of 2 per partner (28)
Dissemination Events	1 st International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy joint event with InNoPlastic H2020 project	03/06/2020	50
	2 nd International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy, joint event with InNoPlasticsH2020 project	06/2022	70
	3 rd International Workshop Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy, joint event with InNoPlastic H2020 project	06/2023	
	MAELSTROM Final Workshop & Conference – Porto, Portugal	2024	
Clean ups & Info Days	Yearly clean ups (4 in total) & Info Day - Venice, Italy on World Ocean/World Environmental Day	05/06/2021 02/06/2022 06/2023 06/2024	50 50
	Yearly clean ups (4 in total) & Info Day - Porto, Portugal on World Clean Up Day	17/09/2021 09/2022 09/2023 09/2024	100
	Yearly clean ups (2 in total) & Info Day – San Sebastian, Spain	08/2022 06/2023	
Demonstration Workshops	Yearly side events (3 in total) – Venice, at the International Venice Boat Show dedicated to local stakeholders	06/2022 06/2023 06/2024	30
	Side event – Porto, at the Business2Sea	11/2023	

Webinars	Science and society Science and society: working together to address the marine litter challenge	18/11/2021	63
	Localize and Characterize Building Capacity in Detecting, Tracking and Modelling Marine Litter through European Open Science Cloud (#EOSC) Digital Services	10/05/2022	26
	Collect and Remove	10/2022	
	Sort and Transform	04/2023	
	Marketize	10/2023	
	Topic TBA	04/2024	
	Topic TBA	10/2024	
Capacity Building Actions	Capacity Building on Communication & Stakeholder Engagement approaches. Target: MAELSTROM's partners/communication focal points	Replaced by monthly meetings	Communication Focal Points (average 15 people/month)
	Marine litter monitoring using the MAELSTROM App - 2022	2022	60
	Marine litter monitoring using the MAELSTROM App - 2023	2023	
	MAELSTROM's technologies - instructions for use, managing and maintenance - 2023		

Table 7 - External Events & Conferences attended in the first eighteen months

Title	Link	Partner attending
ITEM project online workshop	https://www.cnr.it/it/progetti-di-ricerca/progetto/40295/ctn02-00059-9948371-item-dit-ad022-173	13/01/2021 CNR
EU Biovoices Project Conference	https://www.biovoices.eu/#	14/01/2021 CNR
Blue Med Final Conference	http://www.blumed-initiative.eu/blumed-final-conference/	22-23-24/02/2021 CNR
Ecosistemas Marinhos e Economia Azul	https://ambienteportugal.pt/eventos/ecosistemas-marinhos-e-economia-azul	23/04/2021 CIIMAR
marGnet and MAELSTROM Demonstration activity: operation of a prototype for recycling of marine waste and the production of maritime fuel		14/05/2021 CNR
European Maritime Day - Session BLUINVEST	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/events/2021-european-maritime-day_en	21/05/2021 CNR
NCR May Lecture – Netherlands Centre for River Studies	https://ncr-web.org/events/ncr-may-lecture/	26/05/2021 Deltares
EU Cluster Meeting on projects dealing with 'Marine Litter'	https://bioplasticseurope.eu/media/pages/news-events/horizon-2020-cluster-meeting-on-marine-litter/21c23f102f-1646989939/agenda.pdf	01/06/2021 CNR
Venice International Boat Show	Infopoint on Marine litter	29/05/2021 - 6/06/2021 CNR
Online seminar in the framework of the event "Arazzi del Mare"	Online seminar	8 /06/2021 CNR
AreaAperta Primavera	https://comunicazione.cnr.it/evento/398/evento-conferenza-areaaperta	16/06/2021 CNR
BlueMed Hackathon 2021	https://www.cnr.it/it/news/10199/una-sfida-tra-idee-il-blumed-hackathon-ideas-and-solutions-for-a-healthy-plastic-free-mediterranean-sea	17/06/2021 CNR
EMRA2021 Robotics	https://emra-21.marinerobotics.eu/	08/07/2021 CNR
BlueMed - Unlocking the potential of Ports and Harbours in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter	http://www.blumed-initiative.eu/ports-harbours-venice-september-14-2021/	14/09/2021 CNR
"Arazzi del Mare" organized by QUANTIA - ITALIA	Seminar on marine litter	24/09/2021 CNR

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Innovation Platform "Sustainable Sea and Ocean Solutions ISSS"	https://www.fraunhofer.de/en/research/lighthouse-projects-fraunhofer-initiatives/innovation-platform-sustainable-subsea-solutions.html	23/09/2021 TECNALIA
IHOBE Comisión Basura Marina para el país vasco	https://www.ihobe.eus/agenda/urban-klima-2050-colaboracion-multisectorial-para-financiar-y-reducir-brecha-adaptacion-en-pais-vasco-2?fbclid=IwAR1eN9T4nlTIs8hUlvv3hPz8jjBD4YpUe1gyKqZCzuacujWllOzHm_448Q	28/09/2021 TECNALIA
Scienza in Villa	https://www.scienzainvilla.com	01/10/2021 – 03/10/2021 CNR-ISMAR
ECOMONDO 2021- Transforming plastic litter into new chemicals? Opportunities and challenges for innovative pyrolysis plants	https://www.ecomondo.com/link/seminari-e-convegni/e18938877/transforming-plastics-litter-into-new-chemicals-opportunities-and-challenges-for-innovative-pyrolysis-plants.html	26/10/2021 CNR
ECOMONDO 2021 -The BlueMed Pilot healthy plastics-free Mediterranean Sea towards the 2030 targets: the strategy developed by the plastic producing and transforming operators of the area	http://www.blueded-initiative.eu/pilot-ecomondo-2021-rimini/	26/10/2021 CNR
ECOMONDO 2021 - Connecting the system of Ports and Harbours to unlock the potential in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter across the Mediterranean Sea	http://www.blueded-initiative.eu/ecomondo-2021-oct-27/	27/10/2021 CNR
Workshop EMFF Integration, Scaling Up and Cooperation with other EU Funding Instruments	https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/maritimeforum/en/node/7000?fs=e&se=cl	03/02/2022 CNR
EXPO Dubai: Multidisciplinary and systemic approaches for the rational use of resource and sustainability	https://www.isafom.cnr.it/index.php/en/attivita/divulgazione/tutte-le-news/373-dubai-expo-2020-land-city-sea-scape-intelligence-multidisciplinary-and-systemic-approaches-for-the-rational-use-of-resource-and-sustainability	14/03/2022 CNR
Jornadas do Mar: New Solutions for the Sustainable Removal and Management of Marine Litter	https://www.jornadasdomar.com/schedule	26/03/2022 CIIMAR
The Trash Cycle Initiative – Vila do Conde Clean Up	https://theplastichike.org/the-trash-cycle/	03/06/2022
XI Edition of the Environment Forum: "Removal and Sustainable Management of Marine Litter: Rethinking the Present, Designing the Future"	https://sigarra.up.pt/feup/pt/noticias_geral.ver_noticia?p_nr=130450	05/04/2022 CIIMAR

MAELSTROM

GEOHAB 2022 – Marine Geological & Biological Mapping	https://geohab.org/geohab-2022/	16/05/2022-20/05/2022 CNR
EMRA Workshop "European Marine Robotics & Applications Workshop (EMRA) 2022"	https://noc-events.co.uk/emra-2022	16/06/2022 TECNALIA
AUTOMATION & ROBOTIC TALKS – within BIEMH22 trade fair	https://biemh.bilbaoexhibitioncentre.com/en/conferences/automation-robotic-talks/	17/06/2022 TECNALIA
PLASTICA E CAMBIAMENTI CLIMATICI, UN MARE DA DIFENDERE (Meeting co-organized with UNESCO, Greenpeace Italia and the NGO We are here Venice)	https://www.cnr.it/it/nota-stampa/n-11193/plastica-e-cambiamenti-climatici-un-mare-da-difendere	22/06/2022 CNR
UN Ocean Conference Localizing Action for the Ocean: Local and Regional Governments Special Event	https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2022-04/Concept%20Note%202022%20UNOC%20Local%20and%20Regional%20Gov%20Forum_REVISIED_7April_for%20website%20%281%29.pdf	25/06/2022
UN Ocean Conference Official Session Addressing Marine Pollution	https://sdgs.un.org/events/addressing-marine-pollution-45736	27/06/2022
UN Ocean Conference One Sustainable Ocean-Ocean Science & Business2Sea Side Event	https://oceansciencebusiness2sea.b2match.io/	28/06/2022
UN Ocean Conference <i>EU4OceanObs: Integrating Marine Litter Monitoring to Inform Action</i>	https://www.eu4oceanobs.eu/marine-litter-monitoring-to-inform-action/	29/06/2022
UN Ocean Conference The Charter for the Mission "Restores our Ocean and Waters by 2030"	https://ec.europa.eu/info/events/charter-mission-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-2030-2022-jun-30_en	30/06/2022
ERF2022 – European Robotics Forum – Marine Robotics Workshop + Sustainable Robotics workshop	https://erf2022.eu/	28-29/06/2022 TECNALIA

As part of its dissemination efforts, in January 2022, MAELSTROM's consortium applied to the [Industry 5.0 Award](#): an EU prize that recognizes projects that advance the Industry 5.0 vision by presenting convincing and inspiring solutions. The award addressed three main pillars: sustainability, human-centricity and resilience, while also being clearly applicable in industry. Although the project did not win the prize, MAELSTROM wishes to be part of the Industry 5.0 efforts and thus will organize a

virtual workshop (indicatively October 2022) to gather projects and initiatives to further advance the Industry 5.0. vision.

Future main events in 2022

- **7th International Marine Debris Conference** | Busan, Korea | 18-23 September

<https://www.7imdc.org>

- **Estuarine Coastal Conference** | San Sebastian | 5-8 September 2022

<http://www.estuarinecoastalconference.com/>

- **Ecomondo** | Rimini, Italy | 8-11 November 2022,

<https://www.ecomondo.com>

Young Generations

Besides having a strong presence at scientific and technological events, MAELSTROM also wishes to create awareness in younger generations, having developed some actions with schools in Venice. During the school year 2021-2022, three seminars and a field activity on marine litter clean-up and monitoring were implemented with 2 classes of the Albert Einstein High School. The activities were part of the civic education program to raise student awareness on marine litter and to show the technological solutions that MAELSTROM's project partners are developing. Students were also asked during their daily activities to think about which disposable plastic products could be replaced with other more sustainable materials and to share their ideas and solutions in a specially created WhatsApp chat. Below are the details of the activities conducted with the classes (total of about 45 participants per event/activity).

1. Seminar on marine litter and its impact on ecosystems (online, January 27, 2022)
2. Seminar on microplastics and their impact on ecosystems (in-person, February 17, 2022).
3. Focus on the GHOST, marGnet and MAELSTROM projects (online April 28, 2022).
4. Participation in a clean-up campaign in Pellestrina beach in collaboration with MAELSTROM project partner Venice Lagoon Plastic Free (May 26, 2022).

Figure 16 - Seminar on microplastics at the Albert Einstein High School of Venice, February 2022

Figure 17 - Clean up activity in Pellestrina Beach with students from the Albert Einstein High School of Venice, May 2022

8 Internal Communication

As part of the communication activities, significant efforts are made towards building a participatory and supportive environment among the consortium's members –we consider this a key element in the success of both communication efforts and of the project itself. The decision to substitute a one-off capacity building workshop on communication (initially planned for the kick-off meeting if this was to happen online) by monthly meetings proved to be beneficial, as it allows regular contact among communication focal points and permits their needs and suggestions to be dealt with in a timely manner. At the date of this report, sixteen communication meetings have been carried out, each focusing on a specific topic and all allowing for open discussions and participatory brainstorming regarding communication approaches related to MAELSTROM activities. Communication meetings are called via email by the communication coordinator (CIMA) which asks to focal points to indicate their availability using the Doodle platform; once the date is set, the meeting takes place online, using the MS Teams platform. As well as a regular monthly meeting, complementary meetings are also set within smaller working groups whenever necessary (e.g. only partners involved in a specific event). Considering the positive results, the communication team intends to maintain general monthly meetings as well as specific meetings among project partners.

9 Conclusions and next steps

The present document details and shows the positive outcomes of the communication and dissemination activities implemented so far. Despite the physical distance between the communication team and all other partners, which sometimes presents a challenge when it comes to achieving good outreach in an ever-growing collaborative environment among partners – particularly challenging is allowing for efficient external communication and dissemination results. Future steps will focus on maintaining a good internal communication flow as it represents the basis of external communication and dissemination efforts.

Overall goals regarding external communication and dissemination activities will be:

1. To increase the number of **general articles** on relevant magazines and newspapers, such as *The Guardian*, *EU Horizon Magazine* and other science-based (but not peer-reviewed) magazines

Target: 2 published articles on MAELSTROM's technologies by the end of 2023

2. Increase the number of site visits and **followers** on social media and their interactions with MAELSTROM posts

Target: increase by 100% the number of social media followers by the end of 2023

3. Create opportunities to showcase MAELSTROM activities and technologies on **international TV channels** such as *EURO News*, *BBC* and local channels mainly in Italy, Portugal, and Spain.

Target: 1 dedicated reportage on an international or nationally relevant TV broadcast by the end of 2023.

4. Participate at **international festivals**, such as the New European Bauhaus initiative, and in other international media activities such as documentaries, podcasts, artistic and public events to showcase MAELSTROM's innovations and increase awareness on marine litter and circular economy possibilities

Target: 2 international events by the end of 2023

Detailed goals and indicators will be provided in the Final version of the Plan for Communication and Dissemination report to be delivered by month 24 (31/12/2022).

ANNEX 1 - Communication and dissemination procedures regarding third parties' involvement

The communication and dissemination guidelines regarding the involvement of Third Parties follow two different approaches depending if referring to institutional/in-kind parties or to monetary/financing third parties.

A shared table regarding third parties' involvement was created on the MAELSTROM project channel on MS Teams where partners are expected to insert information and details regarding Parties willing to be involved in the project's activities. It was agreed that partners wishing to establish partnerships with third parties for activities happening within the MAELSTROM project shall inform the Project Manager (CNR-ISMAR) beforehand which, in case of possible ethical issues or conflict of interests will activate the Steering Committee to demand for a shared analysis and final decision.

Institutional and In-Kind Parties

Whenever requested and if considered to benefit a foreseen action and group of partners, every institutional/in-kind support will be fully acknowledged on communication materials. If requested, either by the third party or by the affiliated partner, third party's logos can be placed on MAELSTROM's communication materials (ex. Venice or Porto Municipalities logos), tagged on social media, and mentioned on press releases or in relevant project's events and activities. Approval will need to be previously given by the Project Manager/Consortium.

In the case that the institutional/in-kind support offered is considered to benefit only one partner, the communication process shall occur independently from MAELSTROM's communication group and shall be led by the affiliated partner responsible for the partnership/agreement. In this case, if the support received by the partner will be used for MAELSTROM-related activities, the project name and the European Union co-financing shall be mentioned, without creating a visual association (no logos together). In case the partner uses the support received for activities that do not relate to the MAELSTROM project, no mention to the project or the European Union shall be made.

Figure A1 - Communication procedures regarding institutional and in-kind third parties' involvement

Monetary/Financing Third Parties

Whenever requested, and if considered to benefit a group of partners, every monetary/financial support will be fully full acknowledged on communication materials. If requested, either by the third party or the affiliated partner, third party's logos can be placed on MAELSTROM's communication materials, tagged on social media and mentioned on press releases or in relevant project's events and activities. Approval will need to be previously given by the Project Manager/Consortium.

In the case monetary/financial support is considered to benefit only one partner, the communication process shall occur independently from MAELSTROM's communication group and shall be led by the affiliated partner responsible for the partnership/agreement. If the support received by the partner is to be used for MAELSTROM-related activities, the project name and the European Union co-financing percentages shall be mentioned, without creating a visual association (no logos together). Moreover, the partner benefiting from the monetary support shall clearly state the co-funding proportion being received, based on the total funding received by the European Union within the MAELSTROM project. In the case that the partner uses the support received for activities not related to the MAELSTROM project, no mention to the project or the European Union shall be made.

Figure A2 - Communication procedures regarding financial third parties' involvement

Figure A3 - Communication procedures regarding third parties' involvement graph flow

ANNEX 2 - MAELDROPS

MAELDrop #1 | The problem of marine litter | April 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-1-the-problem-of-marine-litter/>

Day after day, coming together, raindrops fill the rivers and run into the sea. In the same way, we also want to create information drops which will fill our heads with thoughts, ideas and solutions related to marine litter and to MAELSTROM's goals: please welcome MAELDrops! How does marine litter damage the coastal ecosystems? Are all plastics the same? What can we do to limit this problem, and how does MAELSTROM aim to tackle it?

So, let's get started, come along with us and be part of the move!

Seas and **oceans** play an important role for our planet. They influence the climate, support the life of many species and sustain fundamental human activities. However, the well-being of marine ecosystems is put at risk by several anthropogenic factors, including **litter**.

Litter, whether lost directly along the coastline or delivered to the sea by rivers, wind, or urban run-off, has an important ecological impact on marine life. As highlighted in a report published by the European Commission's JRC, litter can cause **direct damage**, for example by entangling or blocking the stomach/intestine of animals that accidentally ingest it. Moreover, the litter can cause **indirect damage**, for example by inducing a false sense of satiation, acting as vectors for toxic substances and compromising the animals' general ability to feed themselves.

Among marine litter, **plastics** are the most abundant. These are both large fragments and waste or very small particles resulting from the degradation and fragmentation of larger items. These are the microplastics, smaller than 5 mm, which accumulate along the food web and, as a result, can even reach the food we consume.

What will MAELSTROM do to mitigate the litter issue? Our project will develop and test new environmentally sustainable technologies for removing litter accumulated on the seafloor or in the water column in coastal areas. MAELSTROM will then define and implement an integrated assessment approach (IAA) to evaluate the effectiveness of these technologies. This approach will support the Marine Strategy Framework Directive of European Union and assess the positive and/or negative impact of the MAELSTROM litter remediation actions on coastal marine ecosystems and local economies. The IAA will consider both macro and microlitter.

MAELSTROM

SEAS AND OCEANS play an
IMPORTANT ROLE
FOR OUR PLANET

but they are put at risk by
several anthropogenic factors
including litter

PLASTICS are the most
abundant including
microplastics which
accumulate along
the food web and can

REACH
THE FOOD
WE CONSUME

MAELDROPS

#1

LITTER can cause both
direct and indirect

DAMAGE TO
MARINE LIFE

compromising animals
general well-being

MAELSTROM aims to mitigate this
issue by testing technologies for

LITTER REMOVAL FROM
COASTAL ECOSYSTEMS

preventing its accumulation
and degradation

MAELDrop #2 | How much litter is in the sea? | May 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-2-how-much-litter-is-in-the-sea/>

In [MAELDrop #1](#), we have introduced you to the problem of marine litter. But what kind of litter is marine litter? And in which quantities is it present in the oceans?

The United Nation Environment Programme [defines](#) marine litter as “any persistent, manufactured or processed solid material discarded, disposed of or abandoned in the marine and coastal environment”. As we reported, the majority of it is plastics. Assessing the amount of plastics in the sea is not easy, as estimates can give different results depending on the methodology used.

[According to the European Commission](#), more than 150 million tons of plastic are accumulated in the oceans and unfortunately, these quantities are increasing: between 4.6 and 12.7 million tons of plastic are added each year, and it could reach 29 million tons by 2040.

These are impressive numbers, which should be considered even more worrisome considering that most marine litter consists of materials that degrade slowly. As a result, their continuous and increasing dispersion in the seas leads to a **progressive accumulation**. In this way the marine litter becomes pervasive in all the environments increasing the risks for all the food web and the habitats.

What will MAELSTROM do to mitigate the accumulation of marine litter? There are two activities in our project that will help reduce marine litter. On the one hand, we will test and implement two innovative technologies that will allow for the removal of litter from the seabed and from the superficial layers of the water column – we will present them to you soon! But we can't tackle the problem with technology alone – we need shared good practices and everyone's help to preserve our marine ecosystems. Being so, as part of the project we have organized info days and clean up campaigns where we will not be only collecting litter that has accumulated on the coast, but also creating awareness regarding marine litter impacts and spreading good behaviors to mitigate its impacts in coastal ecosystems and in our life!

MAELSTROM

More than **150 MILLION TONS OF PLASTIC** are accumulated in the oceans

These **QUANTITIES ARE INCREASING.**

Between **4.6 and 12.7 MILLION TONS** of plastic are added each year

Since most marine litter consists of **MATERIALS THAT DEGRADE SLOWLY**, there is a **PROGRESSIVE ACCUMULATION** in the seas

MAELSTROM will test and implement two innovative **TECHNOLOGIES FOR LITTER REMOVAL.**

But we can't tackle the problem with technology alone: discover **WHAT YOU CAN DO TO HELP US!**

STAY TUNED...

MAELDrop #3 | Marine litter, from the sea back to the coast | June 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-3-marine-litter-from-the-sea-back-to-the-coast/>

In the last **MAELDrops**, we've told how much litter is found in the seas and oceans, and the damage it causes to ecosystems. But waste doesn't just stay in the water....

Carried by winds and rivers, or even abandoned directly in the sea, currents can concentrate waste, accumulating in large areas, as the famous **Great Pacific Garbage Patch**. But not all litter remains at sea. Ocean currents, in fact, often bring it back to shore ... and so we find it on our coasts and beaches. In addition to representing a possible **economic and landscape damage** (who likes to sunbathe surrounded by garbage?), here too litter can put at risk our ecosystems. According to a recent **technical report** by the European Union's JRC, a beach can be considered clean if less than 20 pieces of trash are found every 100 linear meters of coastline: this is a significant value, if we consider that between 2015 and 2016 many European beaches had on average 150 objects every 100 meters.

Understanding how much and what type of waste is found along the coasts is important to design effective strategies and policies aimed at reducing it. In this sense, **clean up campaigns are a tool of enormous importance**, because on the one hand they help to clean beaches and, on the other hand, they contribute to collect data on the marine litter. In addition, they represent a valuable opportunity to raise public awareness on the problem of marine litter.

What about MAELSTROM? We too believe in the importance of clean ups! The problem of marine litter, in fact, cannot be addressed only with science and technology: all citizens can commit to reduce it, both through small daily gestures and by participating in the clean up events... Like the one that will be held in **June 5th in Venice!** Stay tuned to learn more, in the coming days we will provide all the information about the event, the first – but certainly not the last – of our project!

NOT ALL LITTER REMAINS AT SEA :
ocean currents often bring it back to shore ... and so we **FIND IT ON OUR COASTS AND BEACHES.**

CLEAN UP CAMPAIGNS
are a tool of enormous importance : **THEY HELP TO CLEAN BEACHES...**

...contribute **TO COLLECT DATA ON THE MARINE LITTER** and represent a valuable opportunity to raise **PUBLIC AWARENESS.**

WHAT ABOUT MAELSTROM?
We too believe in the importance of clean up campaign - as the one that will be held in **JUNE 5th IN VENICE :**
stay tuned, in the coming days we will provide all the information about this **FIRST BUT CERTAINLY NOT THE LAST EVENT!**

MAELDrop #4 | Many types of plastics | July 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-4-many-types-of-plastics/>

In our MAELDrops, we have mentioned that most of the marine litter is plastic. But what exactly is plastic?

Plastics are a set of polymeric materials, made up of many equal and repeated units. There are diverse types of plastics and each one has distinct characteristics according to the type of polymer from which it is made. Even in a simple bottle of water we can find two types of plastics: the bottle itself is usually made of polyethylene terephthalate (PET), which is light and resistant, whereas the cap is often made of polypropylene (PP), which is slightly harder and more heat resistant.

Plastics play an important role for human activities. Just think, for example, of how many medical devices, from disposable gloves to catheters, are made of plastic. However, if not responsibly managed and disposed, plastics can become a severe problem for ecosystems, with impacts on our own health. One of the strategies to mitigate the problem, in addition to limiting production whenever possible, is to recycle and re-use plastic materials within in a circular economy perspective. To do so, it is necessary to consider the distinct types of plastics and choose appropriate recycling treatments accordingly.

What about MAELSTROM? From the marine litter collected by our technologies, plastics will be separated thanks to a robot based on an artificial intelligence system. In accordance with the European circular economy action plan, plastics will then be recycled through 3 innovative processes: additive and compounding, hot pressing, and low temperature pyrolysis, which will allow to recycle most of the plastic waste. Materials which will not be directed to recycling will be used for primary energy generation and second-generation fuel, and will power MAELSTROM's underwater cable-robot for marine waste collection... creating a self-sustaining cycle!

NOT ALL PLASTICS ARE THE SAME!

There are diverse types of plastics, with distinct **CHARACTERISTICS AND PROPERTIES**

COLLECTING AND RECYCLING PLASTICS ARE KEY

to limit its accumulation on ecosystems, but it requires **PROPER IDENTIFICATION AND SORTING**

MAELSTROM will use a **ROBOT BASED ON AI TO SEPARATE PLASTICS** from the waste collected in rivers' hotspots in Italy and Portugal

Based on single characteristics it will direct plastic waste to **INNOVATIVE RECYCLING PROCESSES**, or when not compatible, it will use it to power MAELSTROM's technologies, creating **A SELF-SUSTAINING CYCLE!**

MAELDrop #5 | Let's talk about polyethylene | November 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-5-lets-talk-about-polyethylene/>

Some time ago [we mentioned](#) the fact that there is not just one type of plastic, but many, each one of them with its own properties that influence their recycling feasibility. Among the several widespread plastics we use daily, today we will focus on **polyethylene**. Why?

Firstly, because polyethylene is a very versatile polymer, which can be molded into many different shapes and objects, both for everyday and industrial uses [1]. Some examples are: kitchen objects such as jugs or cutting boards, children's toys in parks, drainpipes, and many others, in a very long list. The second reason is that polyethylene is completely recyclable which, considering its wide diffusion, makes it an important type of plastic to consider in terms of circular economy!

It is for this reason that we have chosen recycled polyethylene as the material to make our MAELSTROM mascot whales! We have already introduced you one of the three sperm whales that will accompany us in the next years of work last September, during the [Clean Up in Porto](#), organized by our partner [CIIMAR](#). More two family members will follow soon!

The whales were made possible thanks to the support of the Italian [consortium Ecopolietilene](#) and will help us to disseminate knowledge on marine litter impacts on coastal ecosystems and on sharing good practices regarding innovative plastic removal and recycling technologies. In this way, we will join forces to protect habitat of our sperm whales and of the many other marine species put at risk by the accumulation of marine litter!

POLYETHYLENE is one of the most common types of plastics...and one of the **MOST RECYCLABLE TOO !**

It is therefore a **GOOD RESOURCE** from a **CIRCULAR ECONOMY** perspective.

That's why **MAELSTROM** has used recycled polyethylene to make **ITS SPERM WHALE MASCOTS !**

Which will join us in **SPREADING KNOWLEDGE** on **MARINE LITTER** impacts & **PLASTIC REMOVAL AND RECYCLING** technologies !

HDPE

MAELDROPS #5

MAELDrop #6 | The nexus between plastic and climate change | December 2021

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-6-the-nexus-between-plastic-and-climate-change/>

The United Nations conference on climate change, COP26, has just concluded, confirming the commitment to try to keep the increase in the average global temperature within 1.5 C at the end of the century. There is much to do to achieve this goal, and there are many fronts on which to act. Plastic production is among them.

In fact, as the UNEP report “[From Pollution to Solution: a global assessment of marine litter and plastic pollution](#)” published a few days before the start of COP26 highlights that plastic production led to the emission of 1.7 gigatonnes of CO₂ equivalent in 2015. The authors estimate, moreover, that this figure will increase by about 6.5 times by 2050, reaching an amount that is around 15% of the global carbon budget.

In addition to the risks that plastics poses to ecosystems and to human health, which we have discussed in [MAELDrop 1](#), we must consider that plastics also pose a threat to climate crisis mitigation.

The report also warns that, by 2040, the volume of plastic in the sea could triple. Meanwhile, recycling rates remain below 10%, and unfortunately biodegradable plastics are unlikely to be a solution to the problem. These materials have long degradation times, during which they pose risks to ecosystems as it happens with non-biodegradable plastics. For this reason, the report concludes that synergistic interventions are needed to address the problem. These include circular economy approaches, but also initiatives aimed at changing consumer’s behaviors regarding single-use plastics.

What about MAELSTROM? Our mission is perfectly in line with the report’s conclusions: in fact, we develops solutions to face the problem of the plastic already accumulated in the coastal environment acting on the entire “life cycle” of marine litter: we aim at understanding where marine litter is concentrated, identify it by type, remove it, recycle it and insert it back into the market chain. Following a circular economy approach plastics will be given a new life while avoiding the production of new plastic and in this way protecting coastal ecosystems and our climate.

MAELSTROM

A new **UNEP REPORT**, published a few days before the start of COP26, highlights that in 2015 **PLASTIC PRODUCTION** led to the emission of **1.7 GIGATONNES OF CO₂ EQUIVALENT**

PLASTIC IS THEREFORE A THREAT not only to ecosystems and human health but also to **CLIMATE CRISIS MITIGATION**

Synergistic interventions are needed to address the problem. These include **CIRCULAR ECONOMY** approaches but also initiatives aimed at changing **CONSUMER'S BEHAVIOURS** regarding **SINGLE-USE PLASTICS**

MAELSTROM'S MISSION is in line with the report's conclusions: we act on the entire **"LIFE CYCLE" OF MARINE LITTER**, from **IDENTIFICATION** to **RECYCLING** and **MARKETIZING !**

MAELDrop #7 | How the COVID-19 pandemics increases plastic generation and dispersion | February 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-7-how-the-covid-19-pandemics-increases-plastic-generation-and-dispersion/>

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the importance of plastics, as most protective and medical devices are, at least partially, made of it. At the same time, however, it has exacerbated the problem of plastic pollution due to the increased production and dispersion of protective devices, single-use plastics and plastic packaging in natural ecosystems. Moreover, the need for personal protective equipment has in some cases led to the delay or withdraw of national legislations against single-use plastic.

The relationship between COVID-19 and plastic generation and dispersal was already intuited at the beginning of the pandemic. Scientists are now beginning to quantify it: according to a recent paper, as of August 2021, COVID-19 had led to the production of approximately 8.4 million tons of plastic globally; 25.9 thousand tons of which ended up in the sea. The research has also identified a dozen rivers that transported 79% of the COVID-19-generated plastic into the oceans.

These and future data are of foremost importance as they indicate critical points on which to act and to focus global efforts. In general, however, the authors conclude by reiterating the need already expressed by many experts: technologies to improve the collection, treatment and recycling of plastic are urgently needed.

This is exactly our goal at MAELSTROM! The innovative technologies being developed by our consortium will contribute to improve the plastic management cycle by identifying and removing it from rivers and the seabed. Moreover, the recently launched MAELSTROM app will help operators to track the entire process, from litter identification up to its recycling outcomes. Environmental assessments and monitoring activities happening at the same time alongside the project will enable the identification of accumulation hotspots and will assess the impact of MAELSTROM technologies.

MAELSTROM

<p>COVID-19 has exacerbated the PROBLEM OF PLASTIC IN MARINE ECOSYSTEMS, increasing the PRODUCTION and DISPERSION of protective devices and packaging</p>	
<p>This highlights once more the NEED TO PROMOTE TECHNOLOGIES to improve marine litter IDENTIFICATION, COLLECTION, TREATMENT and RECYCLING</p>	

MAELDrop #8 | Studying marine litter from above with remote sensing | March 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-8/>

Understanding how much waste is present in the oceans, which trajectories it follows and where it accumulates is an essential step to understand its impacts on marine and coastal ecosystems and to set solutions to remove it. However, this is far from easy considering the vast ocean surface and the difficulty to physically access some areas. An important help in this sense comes from remote sensing technologies.

The [European Space Agency](#) (ESA) is funding 26 innovative projects to improve marine litter knowledge and monitoring [through remote sensing](#). Projects [cover different geographic areas and work on several fronts](#), including the development of new data processing, modelling and experimental techniques, mostly based on artificial intelligence.

MAELSTROM fully supports such initiatives. Even if our project works mainly “from the ground” we are convinced that the research activities supported by ESA will not only provide valuable information regarding litter accumulation hotspots on where to focus removal efforts, but they will also open the way to innovative ways to understand the quantities and dynamics of plastics in the environment and how they change in time. Two of MAELSTROM partners are involved in those ESA projects: CNR-ISMAR participates on the [TRACE](#) project, exploring the possibility to detect marine litter from satellite data and forecast their trajectories using a coupled system of water current forecast and marine litter dispersal model. Deltares, on the other hand, is leading the “Plastic Monitor” project, focused on the detection of floating plastic litter that is transported downstream, in very polluted rivers, such as the Citarum river, in Indonesia.

MONITORING THE VAST OCEAN surface to **UNDERSTAND MARINE LITTER QUANTITIES AND DYNAMICS** is not easy

An **IMPORTANT HELP** comes from **ESA** which is funding **MARINE LITTER PROJECTS** THROUGH **REMOTE SENSING**

MAELSTROM fully supports such initiative, as it will open the way to better **IDENTIFY ACCUMULATION HOTSPOTS**

And to better understand the **QUANTITIES AND DYNAMICS OF MARINE LITTER** in the environment and **HOW IT CHANGES IN TIME**

MAELDrop #9 | Cetaceans, between yesterday's risks and today's risks May 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maeldrop-9-cetaceans-between-yesterdays-risks-and-todays-risks/>

Moby Dick classic novel presents a rich description of what was known about whaling and cetaceans at the time of author Herman Melville (1851); some of those descriptions may seem odd for a reader today! For example, Melville wrote that hunting sperm whales would not lead to the decline of their populations as species were considered to be immortal.

Unfortunately, the facts did not prove him right. In the XIX and XX centuries, when cetaceans were hunted mainly for their fat which would be transformed into oil (and that of sperm whales was particularly appreciated) and hunting techniques were refined, there was a sharp decline in cetacean populations. In order to protect those animals, in 1986, came into force the ban of the [International Whale Commission](#) (IWC), an intergovernmental body charged with the conservation of whales and the management of whaling. Some states, however, have continued whaling – no longer to obtain blubber from these cetaceans, but to trade their meat.

This activity is condemned by many quarters because it adds to the serious threats that cetaceans already face. A 2018 [report](#) signed by the Environmental International Agency and the Animal Welfare Institute states that human activities put cetaceans at risk both directly and indirectly, sometimes even acting synergistically: habitat degradation, chemical and noise pollution, unintentional entanglement in fishing gear result in a cumulative stress. Among those threats there is also, plastic pollution. According to the report plastic waste often traps animals or/ is ingested. In addition, baleen whales – cetaceans equipped with baleen to filter water – are also exposed to the risks associated with the ingestion of microplastics and associated pollutants.

In short, the activities of human species have created and still create severe damage to cetaceans. For this reason, MAELSTROM has chosen a cetacean as the “mascot” of its activities... a real-size model of a sperm whale calf, made entirely of recycled plastic which will accompany the MAELSTROM team during info days and clean up activities, raising awareness among citizens on the risks that threaten marine ecosystems. The recycled material was kindly donated by the Italian [Ecopolyethylene Consortium](#). If you are in Venice or visiting the [Salone Nautico](#) come and visit us at CNR!

MAELSTROM

PAST WHALING ACTIVITIES led to a **STRONG DECLINE OF CETACEAN POPULATIONS.**

For this reason, **IT HAS BEEN BANNED** even if some States still practice it

Whaling adds to the already many **SERIOUS THREATS THAT CETACEANS FACE** INCLUDING PLASTIC POLLUTION

That's why MAELSTROM has chosen a **SPERM WHALE AS A PROJECT "MASCOT"**: it will accompany our teams on **RAISING AWARENESS OF THE RISKS** posed by plastics to coastal ecosystems

Come and **MEET OUR WHALE IN VENICE**, during our **NEXT WORKSHOP IN JUNE!**

VENICE
JUNE
2022

ANNEX 3 – Newsletters

Newsletter #1

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #1

[View this email in your browser](#)

July, 2021

MAELSTROM Newsletter #1

Welcome to MAELSTROM's project first newsletter! We are pleased to update you on the work we are carrying on, on our past and future events and all other news and milestones from the "MAELSTROM world". But, first of all... if you still don't know what MAELSTROM is about, let us introduce you the project!

What is MAELSTROM?

It is an EU-funded project designed to develop and test innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in coastal environments.

MAELSTROM will identify litter accumulation hotspots in the regions of Venice (Italy) and Porto (Portugal) and will implement two removal technologies – a **Bubble Barrier** and an **Underwater Cable Robot** designed to remove litter from the water column and from the sea/riverbed, respectively. Removal activities will be accompanied by environmental assessment, to understand the impact of marine litter in demo sites and that of the removal operations.

The removed litter will go through advanced recycling processes allowing for regenerated materials - such as polymers - to re-enter the industrial supply chains. At the end, feasibility studies regarding MAELSTROM's tested processes - from litter identification until its marketization - will bring together societal, economic and environmental indicators.

MAELSTROM will also contemplate science-policy interface, public awareness and societies' engagement regarding marine litter global challenge, through multiple events.

To know more, check our video [on YouTube](#) or [on our website](#)!

Our motto is:

Remove. Recycle. Give it a new use. Repeat

Will it be yours too?

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #1

Who are we?

MAELSTROM brings together 14 international partners from 8 EU countries:

MAELSTROM's events

MAELSTROM's Kickoff meeting

Three days of intense work to present goals and activities to be carried out in the next four years. One common aim: **to protect coastal ecosystems** by identifying, removing, recycling, and putting marine litter back in the market chain: discover more about our kick off meeting, held in February 2021!

[Learn More](#)

With In-No-Plastic, our first international event

The workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy: Challenges and Opportunities, held in Venice on June 3rd, was the first joint event of H2020 projects MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic. It was an **important moment to exchange knowledge** and updates on technologies being implemented for the removal and recycling of marine litter.

[Learn More](#)

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #1

Our first joint clean-up campaign in Venice

Strong citizens' participation and **three tons of collected waste**: great achievements on our first MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic joint clean up which took place in Venice during the World Environment Day, on June 5th.

[Learn More](#)

Next step: Porto's clean up event

Alongside the **World Cleanup Day** we will have our next beach clean up happening in September. The event will be organized by our partner CIIMAR and it will take place in Porto (Portugal). Stay tuned through our website and social media to have more details in the following weeks!

[Learn More](#)

MAELSTROM's technologies

The Great Bubble Barrier

Between the 12th and 16th of April, CIIMAR hosted The Great Bubble Barrier team in Northern Portugal, where several estuaries were analyzed towards the implementation of the **Bubble Barrier**. Both parties worked together to identify areas where a major impact can be achieved regarding marine litter removal actions.

Parallely, and in order to learn how the Bubble Barrier functions under different conditions, Deltares conducted some tests in Amsterdam. Bubble Barrier Amsterdam is active since 2019 in one of the main waterways of the Dutch capital preventing plastics from flowing into the North Sea. Deltares' researchers measured the flow velocity through two means: one permanent system at one location and one moving system using a drone. They then analysed the litter collected on a daily basis to see how the amount and composition of waste collected vary with wind and flow conditions.

Some of the litter collected included food wrappers and even a few laminated restaurant menus, for which the source can easily be traced back. The test was conducted with tangerines, a common way to measure floating objects. Using this common method to monitor floating objects, they determined what fraction of the

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #1

tangerines was collected by the Bubble Barrier. The majority was forced to the side of the canal into the catchment system.

Through those tests Deltares and The Great Bubble Barrier teams are able to better understand how the Bubble Barrier will work under different conditions, which will be used to design and deploy the Bubble Barrier in Portugal.

Underwater cable robot

In the past 6 months, an intense activity has been going on between the partners involved in the design of the **robotic system** to remove the marine litter from the seabed (Tecnalia, LIRMM, STVenezia, CNR ISMAR, VLPPF).

Environmental conditions of the Venice lagoon and its surrounding coastal area were evaluated, including depth, tide, currents on the surface and seabed, among others. Paralelly, information regarding the marine litter and plastics items that are expected to be found on the seabed were also collected, discussing it directly within local consortium's partners CNR- ISMAR and VLPPF, as well as with other external partners. Technical requirements regarding the sensors to be integrated in the robot (cameras, DVL, IMU, GPS, ADCP etc.), have also been defined so that the latter can be teleoperated from the surface and, in the future, be autonomously piloted by artificial intelligence and automatic control software.

Based on all these requirements, Tecnalia has created different designs of the cable-driven parallel robot mechatronics structure, as well as designs of the robot end-effector that will include a dredge as suction device and an underwater gripper for the grasping of larger items. The optimization of the designs is close to be concluded so that manufacture can start shortly!

MAELSTROM's milestones

Identification of litter hotspot in Venice. CNR-ISMAR has been engaged in the identification marine litter accumulation hotspots in the Venice Lagoon and coastal areas, to identify the most suitable locations to implement MAELSTROM's removal technologies.

MAELSTROM's first field monitoring for stranded marine litter. Heid on the last week end of April, this was the first joint activity for MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic, and the **beginning** of a series of monitoring actions regarding waste stranded along the coasts of the Venice Lagoon. This first assessment was moreover useful to collect ideas and suggestions for the setup of MAELSTROM's marine litter tracking app.

MAELSTROM goes *glocal*. Think globally, act locally: the Environmental Education Center of Cairo Montenotte, in Liguria (Italy), **has engaged some local schools to collect plastic** which will be recycled and processed to be build MAELSTROM's gadgets!

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #1

MAELSTROM's networking

- [ITEM project](#)
- [EU Biovoices Project Conference](#)
- [BlueMed Conference](#)
- [Ecosistemas Marinhos e Economia Azul](#)
- [Chioggia Higher Education School & Fishermen Association](#)
- [European Maritime Day – Session BLUEINVEST](#)
- [NCR May Lecture – Netherlands Centre for River Studies](#)
- [EU Cluster Meeting on projects dealing with Marine Litter](#)
- [Quantia Event](#)
- [AreaAperta Primavera](#)
- [BleMed Hackathon 2021](#)

Co-funded by the European Union

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Newsletter #2

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #2

[View this email in your browser](#)

December, 2021

MAELSTROM Newsletter #2

Welcome to MAELSTROM's second newsletter! If you are new to MAELSTROM, note that it is an EU-funded project bringing together 14 partners from 8 European countries, designed to develop and test innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in coastal environments. Know more about the project [here!](#)

HOW IS IT GOING?

Environmental monitoring

Venice

In the last weeks, [CNR-ISMAR](#) started the environmental assessment in the Venice Lagoon by mapping hotspots of marine litter. CNR-ISMAR also tested different multibeam echosounder systems on the site to achieve the best results using the latest cutting-edge technology (Kongsberg, R2Sonic and Norbit). The maps will be the baseline of the next environmental assessment to be done before the robot implementation.

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #2

collected during the [LIFE-LEMA](#) project for analysis. Moreover, a large effort was done to define the complete robotic cell layout which is expected to be operational during the first semester of 2022 - on time to use the marine litter collected during the Venice summer clean-up on training the AI algorithm on real collected marine litter.

Main public events

In-No-Plastic/MAELSTROM workshop and Clean Up in Venice

The workshop *Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy: Challenges and Opportunities*, the first international event of MAELSTROM and our twin project *In-No-Plastic*, was held in Venice on June 3rd. This was an important moment of knowledge exchange and an opportunity to share updates on recent technologies for the removal and recycling of marine litter. The workshop was followed by a Lagoon clean-up on June 5th, within the World Environment Day.

[Learn More](#)

Porto Clean Up and info day on World Clean Up Day

On the World Clean-up Day, held on September 18th, [CIIMAR](#) and [CIMA Research Foundation](#) partners have organized a beach Clean-up at Castelo do Queijo (Porto). The event was associated with an info day to raise awareness about marine litter related impacts, and it counted with a special guest: our sperm whale! A real-size calf installation entirely made of recycled plastic, that was possible due to the precious help of the Italian Ecopolietilene consortium.

[Learn More](#)

... Last but not least

MAELSTROM FIRST WEBINAR WITHIN THE OCEAN DECADE

Within the United Nations Ocean Decade Laboratories, under the call "A Clean Ocean," the MAELSTROM team organized a satellite activity on *Inspiring Science and Society to tackle Marine Litter*. The event was held on November 18th, 2021, during a one-day online seminar and saw the participation of fifty participants in representation of multiple sectors from academia, private sector, environmental NGOs and Civil Society Organisations (CSOs). As for gender representation, 65% of the participants were women while 43% were men.

During the morning part of the webinar representatives of worldwide multi-scale marine litter initiatives presented the outcomes and the challenges experienced during their implementation efforts. In the afternoon, the webinar followed a participatory approach with discussions among panelists and participants on gaps and opportunities regarding marine litter within four clusters: i) Civic Engagement,

<https://us6.campaign-archive.com/?u=29f791069e98d5d66bc588e28&id=47c2514d5a>

3/6

7/1/22, 4:03 PM

MAELSTROM Newsletter #2

Networking and Communication; ii) Stakeholder Coordination; iii) Governance; and iv) Funding

MAELSTROM APP

On December 11, a joint clean up event between MAELSTROM and the In-No-Plastics projects **closed the testing phase of the MAELSTROM app**. The App was designed to improve the marine litter collection and recycling processes based on more complete and accountable procedures. The App was developed by [GEES recycling](#), [ISDI](#) and [VLPE](#) partners. Read more [here!](#)

JOINT STRATEGY

As part of WP 7, the MAELSTROM team CIMA and CIIMAR have developed a Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions regarding Marine Litter (ML) mitigation initiatives within the European space. The strategy aims at contributing to the **coordination and integration of blue technology for plastic strategy-oriented efforts** by directly collecting the perspectives of ML practitioners and stakeholders on current gaps in the field. It furthermore aims at identifying effective approaches for multi-level stakeholder engagement, hopefully leading to more effective policies and actions regarding marine litter reduction, identification, removal, and recycling. The document will soon be online on MAELSTROM's website!

WHAT'S NEXT?

2022 public event

Next year will take us to Venice (Italy), Porto (Portugal) and San Sebastian (Spain) for more clean ups and info days: stay tuned on our website and social media for updates!

Next webinars

<https://us6.campaign-archive.com/?u=29f791f69e98d8d66bc586e28&id=47c2514d5a>

4/6

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MAELSTROM Newsletter #2

Not only public events: in 2022, we will organize two more webinars regarding marine litter and its challenges, so to increase networking actions across public, private, and societal actors also making use of our Forum: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/forums/forum/maelstrom-forum/>

WHERE HAVE WE BEEN?

June:

- 01: [EU Cluster meeting in project dealing with Marine Litter](#)
- 08: [Quantia](#)
- 16: [Area Aperta](#)

- 17: [BlueMed Hackathon](#)

July

- 08: [EMRA2021 Marine Robotics](#)

September

- 12: [Quantia](#)
- 14: [BlueMed Unlocking the potential of Ports and Harbours in preventing and reducing the effects of Ma](#)
- 23: [Innovation Platform "Sustainable Sea and Ocean Solutions ISSS"](#)

October

- 26/27 [Ecomondo](#)

Our motto is:

Remove. Recycle. Give it a new use. Repeat

Will it be yours too?

Co-funded by
the European Union

<https://us6.campaign-archive.com/?u=29f791f69e98ddd66bc588e28&id=47c2514d5a>

5/6

ANNEX 4 – MAELSTROM EVENTS

- MAELSTROM Kick off meeting, February 3-5, 2021, Online

<https://www.moelstrom-h2020.eu/eu-h2020-moelstrom-kicks-off-to-tackle-marine-litter-in-coastal-ecosystems/>

- 1st International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities – June 3, 2021, Venice, Italy | Joint event with InNoPlastic H2020 project | <https://www.moelstrom-h2020.eu/event/moelstrom-in-no-plastic-workshop/>

- Clean up Venice, Italy – International Environment Day within the EU Green Week, June 5, 2021 | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/maelstrom-in-no-plastic-workshop/>

- Clean up Porto, Portugal – World Clean Up Day, September 18, 2021
<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/beach-clean-up-2/>

- Webinar Science and society: Working together to address the marine litter challenge, November 18, 2021 | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/inspiring-science-and-society-to-tackle-marine-litter/>

- Webinar Localize and Characterize: Building Capacity in Detecting, Tracking and Modelling Marine Litter through European Open Science Cloud (#EOSC) Digital Services, May 10, 2022

- Local Stakeholder meeting & Demonstration event - Venice| May 31, 2022 | Within the International Venice Boat Show | <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/inspiring-science-and-society-to-tackle-marine-litter/>

MAELSTROM

Nuove tecnologie per la gestione dei rifiuti marini a Venezia

Arsenale Torre Alberaria
Salone Nautico di Venezia
31 maggio 2022

Organised by:

In cooperation with:

Co-funded by the European Union

AGENDA

Ore 10:00 Saluto istituzionale e di benvenuto
Comune di Venezia
Salone Nautico
CNR-ISMAR

Ore 10:30 Introduzione ai lavori (F. Madricardo CNR-ISMAR - D. Poletta VLPF)

La Legge Salvomare: svolta per una economia circolare dei rifiuti marini in Italia - Sen. Andrea Ferrazzi, Membro della 13^a Commissione permanente (Territorio, ambiente, beni ambientali)

Le attività del Progetto MAELSTROM a Venezia: Tecnologie innovative per la mappatura, rimozione ed il riciclaggio di macro e microplastiche dai mari

Progetto InNoPlastics: monitoraggio delle macro e micro plastiche nella Laguna

Le attività del Progetto Interreg Italia-Croazia MARLESS nell'area di Venezia

WWF - Comune di Venezia: Strategia Plastic Smart Cities per Venezia

Ore 11:15 *Pausa caffè*

Ore 11:30 Tavola rotonda

Ore 12:30 *Cocktail*

MAELSTROM

www.maelstrom-h2020.eu

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Co-funded by the European Union

- 2nd International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities – June 1, Venice, Italy | Joint event with InNoPlasticsH2020 project

- Clean up Venice – International Environment Day within the EU Green Week, June 2, 2022

<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/event/venice-clean-up-2022/>

ANNEX 5 – EXTERNAL EVENTS

2021

- EU Biovoices Project Conference, 14/01/2021

https://www.biovoices-platform.eu/public/_/viewFile/60130b29ddfbad073c50bbef

- Blue Med Final Conference, 22-23-24/02/2021

<http://www.bluedmed-initiative.eu/bluedmed-final-conference/>

One Mediterranean: practices, results and strategies for a common Sea
BlueMed CSA Final Conference
 22-24 February 2021, on-line: digital hub at CNR in Rome

The Mediterranean Sea is a crucial crossroad for the history, economy and culture of Europe, Middle East and North African countries. Many different interests depend on its resources, and the development of a coordinated plan for a shared, coherent and sustainable management is of paramount importance. Moreover, crucial issues like plastic pollution need to be tackled together by all Mediterranean countries, and pooling all relevant knowledge and people both from research and from the socio-political arena.

The BlueMed Initiative, launched in 2014, addresses these challenges, working on all the relevant levels, stimulating pan-Mediterranean network-building and coordinating thematic platforms. The co-building of a shared Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda, the subsequent goals prioritisation and the development of their Implementation Plans, as well as the outcomes of the Pilot Initiative for a Healthy, Plastic-free Mediterranean Sea, of the Start Up Actions and of the Ambassadors' Programme are the most mature achievements of the BlueMed work and will be presented during the conference.

- Ecosistemas Marinhos e Economia Azul, 23/04/2021

<https://ambienteportugal.pt/event/ecosistemas-marinhos-e-economia-azul>

ENTRA NA ONDA PELO AMBIENTE

CONTRIBUA TO SUSTENTABILIDADE AMBIENTAL SIMAR SO ABB

ebooks gratuitos
passatempos
giveaways
webinars

Dia 23 de abril | Ecosistemas Marinhos e Economia Azul

Oradores e Moderadores: 1º Painel - Sara Duarte - Águas do Tejo Atlântico ...

- marGnet and MAELSTROM Demonstration activity: operation of a prototype for recycling of marine waste and the production of maritime fuel, 14/05/2021

Inaugurazione: punto di sbarco molluschi in Punta Poli
Attività dimostrativa: funzionamento di un prototipo per il riciclo dei rifiuti marini e la produzione di carburante marittimo
progetti marGnet e Maelstrom

Venerdì 14 maggio 2021 - h. 11.30
Punta Poli – Chioggia
in diretta streaming:
<https://www.facebook.com/mercatoitticochioggia>
<https://www.instagram.com/mercatoitticoch/>

Saluti d'apertura
 Sono invitati ad intervenire:
Alessandro Ferro, Sindaco del Comune di Chioggia
Daniele Stecco, Assessore al Bilancio, Partecipate, Politiche Comunitarie, Trasporti, Pesca
Marco Spinadin, Presidente del FLAG Chioggia e Delta del PO
Emanuele Mazzaro, Amministratore Unico e Direttore Generale SST S.p.A.
 Sua Eccellenza **Mons. Adriano Tassarollo**, Vescovo della Diocesi di Chioggia
Gianpaolo Bottacin, Assessore all'Ambiente, Clima, Protezione civile Regione del Veneto
Cristiano Corazzari, Assessore a Territorio, Cultura, Caccia e pesca Regione del Veneto

marGnet e Maelstrom: due progetti per affrontare l'emergenza dei rifiuti marini
Fantina Madricardo, CNR-ISMAR, coordinatrice dei progetti marGnet e Maelstrom

marGnet: un prototipo per il riciclo del marine litter
GianClaudio Faussone, Sintol s.r.l.

Conclusioni e scenari per la riduzione dei rifiuti marini
 Modera l'incontro **Valentina Zambetti**, techneprojects s.r.l.s.

Supporto all'innovazione per progetti e iniziative locali

Finanzia il tuo progetto innovativo. Supporto alla ricerca e all'innovazione per progetti e iniziative locali.

- European Maritime Day - Session BLUINVEST, 21/05/2021
https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/events/2021-european-maritime-day-2021-05-20_en

- NCR May Lecture – Netherlands Centre for River Studies, 26/05/2021
<https://ncr-web.org/events/ncr-may-lecture/>

NCR May Lecture

26 May 2021 - 13:00

Netherlands Centre for River studies **NCR** | May Lecture

Date 26 May, 2021 | 13:00 - 14:00

Lecturer Frans Buschman

Topic Transport and fate of plastic litter in rivers - how can monitoring be supported by modelling?

- EU Cluster Meeting on projects dealing with 'Marine Litter', 01/06/2021

<https://bioplasticseurope.eu/media/pages/news-events/horizon-2020-cluster-meeting-on-marine-litter/21c23f102f-1646989939/agenda.pdf>

EUROPEAN RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA)
 REA.B - Green Europe
B.3 - Biodiversity, Circular Economy and Environment

Cluster meeting on projects dealing with 'Marine Litter'
1st June 2021 (Online, Webex)

Time (CEST)	Agenda item	Speakers
8:45 - 9:00	Connect to Webex & Participation guidelines	Webex Host - RANIERI Marco (REA)
Opening		
9:00 - 9:10	Welcome	ACHILLEOS Evdokia (REA)
9:10 - 9:20	Presentation of the policy officers	Policy officers
Session 1: A common European framework to harmonise procedures for plastics pollution monitoring and assessments.		
9:20 - 9:30	Presentation EUROqCHARM	Prof. VAN BAVEL Bert (NIVA)
9:30 - 9:40	Questions and Answers	Moderator: LAMMENS Veerle (REA) Panel: all participants
Session 2: Plastics in the environment: understanding the sources, transport, distribution and impacts of plastics pollution.		
9:40 - 9:50	Presentation LABPLAS	Prof. BEIRAS Ricardo (UVIGO)
9:50 - 10:00	Questions and Answers	Moderator: LAMMENS Veerle (REA) Panel: all participants
Session 3: Sustainable solutions for bio-based plastics on land and sea.		
10:00 - 10:10	Presentation BIO-PLASTICS EUROPE	Prof. LEAL Walter (HAW Hamburg)
10:10 - 10:20	Presentation SEALIVE	MSc. GALLUR Miriam (ITENE)
10:20 - 10:35	Questions and Answers	Moderator: LAMMENS Veerle (REA) Panel: all participants
10:35 - 10:45	Coffee break	
Session 4: Blue green innovations for clean coasts and seas.		
10:45 - 10:55	Presentation CLAIM	Dr. TRIANTAFYLLOU George (HCMR)
10:55 - 11:05	Presentation GoJelly	Dr. JAVIDPOUR Jamileh (GEOMAR)
11:05 - 11:20	Questions and Answers	Moderator: LAMMENS Veerle (REA) Panel: all participants
Session 5: Pilot action for removal of marine plastics and litter.		
11:20 - 11:30	Presentation In-No-Plastic	Dr. JAHREN Susie (SINTEF)
11:30 - 11:40	Presentation MAELSTROM	Dr. MADRICARDO Fantina (CNR)
11:40 - 11:55	Questions and Answers	Moderator: LAMMENS Veerle (REA) Panel: all participants
Closing		
11:55 - 12:00	Closing remarks	LAMMENS Veerle (REA)

Agence exécutive européenne pour la recherche / Europees Uitvoerend Agentschap voor het onderzoek, 1049 Bruxelles/Brussel, BELGIQUE/BELGIE - Tel. +32 22991 789 - Veerle.LAMMENS@ec.europa.eu

- Venice International Boat Show, 29/05/2021 - 6/06/2021

- BlueMed Hackathon 2021, 17/06/2021

- EMRA2021 Robotics, 08/07/2021

- BlueMed - Unlocking the potential of Ports and Harbours in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter, 14/09/2021

Unlocking the potential of Ports and Harbours in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter

September 14, 2021, CNR ISMAR in Venice and online

This workshop looks at the most promising R&I solutions undertaken, as well as the policy instruments implemented, in the management and valorization of plastic litter in Ports/Harbours and their hinterland at Mediterranean level. The aim of the event is to identify gaps and bottlenecks to be overcome for an effective prevention and mitigation from the impact of marine litter across the whole basin.

Harbours and Marinas, that are among the heavily affected areas by the effects of marine litter, could play a strategic role in the remediation and prevention process from plastic pollution in the long term. Indeed, they act as catalysts for stakeholders across the plastic value chain by favoring the connection and collaboration among the shipping and fisheries sectors, encouraging the availability and adequacy of port reception facilities, as well as the conversion of waste – such as fishing gears – into valuable materials.

Photo by Nick Sansouris on Unsplash

FEDERPESCA

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

Confederación Española de Pesca

Agenda

09:30 – 16:00

OPEN ONLINE EVENT

09:30

Welcome and workshop opening

Sigi Gruber (EC), Fabio Fava (University of Bologna) - *In memory of Emmanuelle*

Lia Santoleri (Director of CNR ISMAR)

Fabio Fava (University of Bologna, Italian BlueMed GSO Working Group delegate)- *The BlueMed Pilot Action for a Healthy Plastic Free Mediterranean Sea*

John Bell (DG-RTD, Healthy Planet Director)

10:10

Setting the scene for the prevention of marine litter towards good performing ports across all the Mediterranean basin

Chair: Eleni Hatziyanni (EC – DG MARE)

Towards a Sustainable Blue Economy in the Mediterranean

Eleni Hatziyanni (EC – DG MARE)

The GFCM 2030 Strategy - Contributing to a healthy Mediterranean and a productive Fisheries and Aquaculture sector

Imad Lahoud (GFCM)

Enhancement of the management of sea-based generated marine litter, in the Mediterranean

Gabino Gonzalez (REMPEC)

EU legislation on port reception facilities

Casto Lopez-Benitez (EC - DG MOVE)

Towards EU 2030 targets

Elisabetta Balzi (EC - DG RTD, BlueMed GSO Working Group delegate)

The Italian policies for the protection of marine environment

Simona Rossi (MiTE)

11:10

Coffee break

11:30

SESSION 1: From waste to resource: building frameworks for circular economy – Projects and Initiatives

Session chair: Sigi Gruber (EC)

The role of the coastguard in supporting coastal protection

Com. Antonio Frigo (C.F. Guardia Costiera)

Monitoring litter on coastal area

Alessandra Giorgetti (INOGS)

New solutions for the removal and recycling of marine litter: From MarGnet to the H2020-MAELSTROM project

Fantina Madricardo (CNR ISMAR)

CLAIM projects: innovative approaches to redefine the ways in which we tackle marine litter

George Triantafyllou (HCMR)

OCEANETS: Technological approaches for circular economy solutions

Sonia Albein Urios (AIMPLAS)

BLUENET: Creating new life for discarded fishing and aquaculture gears to prevent marine litter generation

Oihane Cabezas (AZTI)

NetTag: Tagging fishing gears and enhancing on board best-practices to promote waste free fisheries

Marisa Almeida (CIIMAR)

- Innovation Platform "Sustainable Sea and Ocean Solutions ISSS", 23/09/2021

- IHOBE Comisión Basura Marina para el país vasco, 28/09/2021
https://www.ihobe.eus/agenda/urban-klima-2050-colaboracion-multisectorial-para-financiar-y-reducir-brecha-adaptacion-en-pais-vasco-2?fbclid=IwAR1eN9T4nLTIs8hUlVv3hPz8jBD4YpUe1gyKqZCzuacujWlllOzHm_448Q

- **ECOMONDO 2021 - Transforming plastic litter into new chemicals? Opportunities and challenges for innovative pyrolysis plants, 26/10/2021**

<https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-12/ECOMONDO%20-%20Chemical%20recycling%20-%20summary%20report%20rev%20%282%29.pdf>

<p>10:00 - 13:00</p> <p>Sala Ravezzi 2 Hall Sud</p> <p>BLUE GROWTH Evento con la Commissione Europea</p>	<p>Transforming plastic litter into new chemicals? Opportunities and challenges for innovative pyrolysis plants - VERSIONE IN LINGUA INGLESE</p> <p>Lingua: inglese Traduzione simultanea: italiano</p> <p>Organized by: Ecomondo Scientific Technical Committee and CINEA (Sustainable Blue Economy Unit)</p> <p>The workshop will gather innovators, local and ports authorities, legislators and stakeholders, e.g. plastics association and fishers and vessels, to discuss the opportunities offered by pyrolysis plants to convert plastics waste into new chemicals. At the same time the technical and legislative barriers that hinder the exploitation of this kind of technologies will be addressed. The workshop will tackle plastics coming from different waste streams, and will specifically focus on the use of low temperature pyrolysis plants to treat marine litter.</p>
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- **ECOMONDO 2021 -The BlueMed Pilot healthy plastics-free Mediterranean Sea towards the 2030 targets: the strategy developed by the plastic producing and transforming operators of the area, 26/10/2021**

<https://www.ecomondo.com/eventi/ecomondo-2022/seminari-e-convegni/e20336286/the-blumed-pilot-healthy-plastics-free-mediterranean-sea-and-the-eu-mission-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-by-2030.html>

Home / Eventi / Ecomondo 2022 / Programma Eventi

Ecomondo 2022

The BlueMed Pilot healthy plastics-free Mediterranean sea and the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030

📅 Venerdì 11 Novembre 2022
🏷️ Blue Economy

🕒 10:00 - 13:00

📌 MEMO

📍 Sala Diotallevi 1 Hall Sud

🗣️ inglese

Organized by: Ecomondo Scientific Technical Committee & BlueMed GSOs, Federchimica-PlasticsEurope Italia, Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions (CPMR), National Research Council of Italy (CNR)

- **ECOMONDO 2021 - Connecting the system of Ports and Harbours to unlock the potential in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter across the Mediterranean Sea, 27/10/2021**

https://en.ecomondo.com/ecomondo/programma-eventi/pdf-calendario-eventi/2021/ecomondo-2021_eng_estesa_2010.pdf

14:30 - 17:30

Diotallevi 2 Room South Hall

BLUE GROWTH
Ecomondo Event

Connecting the system of Ports and Harbours to unlock the potential in preventing and reducing the effects of Marine Litter across the Mediterranean - Ecomondo and Blue Sea Land Joint Event - VERSIONE IN LINGUA INGLESE

Language: English
Simultaneous translation: Italian

Organized by: Ecomondo Scientific Technical Committee, Blue Sea Land, Cluster BIG, Federpesca, CNR, BLUEMED GSOs

2022

- Workshop EMFF Integration, Scaling Up and Cooperation with other EU Funding Instruments, 03/02/2022

<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/maritimeforum/en/node/7000?fs=e&s=cl>

“EMFF Integration, Scaling Up and Cooperation with other EU Funding Instruments Workshop”

SYNERGIES AND CLUSTERING BETWEEN MARITIME PROJECTS
NEW IDEAS FOR A SUSTAINABLE BLUE ECONOMY

- EXPO Dubai: Multidisciplinary and systemic approaches for the rational use of resource and sustainability, 14/03/2022

<https://www.isoform.cnr.it/index.php/en/attivita/divulgazione/tutte-le-news/373-dubai-expo-2020-land-city-sea-scape-intelligence-multidisciplinary-and-systemic-approaches-for-the-rational-use-of-resource-and-sustainability>

- Jornadas do Mar: New Solutions for the Sustainable Removal and Management of Marine Litter, 26/03/2022

<https://www.jornadasdomar.com/schedule>

- XI Edition of the Environment Forum: “Removal and Sustainable Management of Marine Litter: Rethinking the Present, Designing the Future”, 05/04/2022

AMBIENTE:
UM IMPULSO À INOVAÇÃO

PROGRAMA

09h Sessão de Abertura

Prof. Augusto Sousa | Vice-Presidente do Conselho Pedagógico
| Presidente Ordem dos Engenheiros Região Norte
Prof. Joana Dias | Diretora da Licenciatura e Mestrado em Engenharia do Ambiente
Carolina Lopo e Maria Carolina Duarte | Presidência da Comissão Organizadora

09h30 Impulso I Compartimentos Ambientais

Moderador: Prof. Cristina Vila
9h30: Dr. Luís Vieira | Remoção e Gestão Sustentável do Lixo Marinho: Repensar o Presente, Projetar o Futuro
9h50: Eng. Teresa Valente | TERRA MATER
10h10: Prof. Romualdo Salcedo | Projeto ACS

COFFEE BREAK

11h Impulso II Indústria em Portugal

Moderador: Prof. Mário Amorim Lopes
11h00: Eng. Ana Cruz | Sustentável por Natureza
11h20: Dr.ª Patrícia Vieira | Valérius 360
11h40: Eng. Miguel Cachão | RedWine – Quando o CO₂ é a Solução

ALMOÇO

5 ABR
GRANDE AUDITÓRIO
DA FEUP

Logos: NE EA, CITEP DO GOVERNO REGIONAL NORTE, LEA PORTO, M.E.A., LEA, ALICE, SUMA

- GEOHAB 2022 – Marine Geological & Biological Mapping, 16-20/05/2022
<https://geohab.org/2022-program/>

- European Marine Robotics & Applications 2022 – Workshop, 16/06/2022
<https://noc-events.co.uk/emra-2022>

- AUTOMATION & ROBOTIC TALKS – within BIEMH22 trade fair, 17/06/2022
<https://biemh.bilbaoexhibitioncentre.com/en/conferences/automation-robotic-talks/>

- **PLASTICA E CAMBIAMENTI CLIMATICI, UN MARE DA DIFENDERE, 22/06/2022**
<https://www.cnr.it/it/nota-stampa/n-11193/plastica-e-cambiamenti-climatici-un-mare-da-difendere>

- **UN Ocean Conference: Localizing Action for the Ocean: Local and Regional Governments Special Event**

https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2022-04/Concept%20Note%202022%20UNOC%20Local%20and%20Regional%20Gov%20Forum_REVISED_7_April_for%20website%20%281%29.pdf

- UN Ocean Conference: One Sustainable Ocean-Ocean Science & Business2Sea Side Event

<https://oceansciencebusiness2sea.b2match.io/>

- UN Ocean Conference: *EU4OceanObs: Integrating Marine Litter Monitoring to Inform Action* <https://www.eu4oceanobs.eu/marine-litter-monitoring-to-inform-action/>

- UN Ocean Conference: The Charter for the Mission “Restores our Ocean and Waters by 2030”

https://ec.europa.eu/info/events/charter-mission-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-2030-2022-jun-30_en

- ERF2022 – European Robotics Forum – Marine Robotics Workshop + Sustainable Robotics workshop

<https://erf2022.eu>

